

Forestry transplants in containers? "Yes", say experts

The starting point for any discussion on forestry transplants for New Zealand and Australia must always be the extraordinary success of the bare-root system developed for *Pinus radiata* seedlings. While this success remains, there is little point in talking about containers for the bulk of the radiata market.

If the bare-root system is so successful, why is there the need to consider other options? Containers are being considered to fulfil certain specific requirements.

Some of these are:

- The extension of the planting season, both into the autumn and into the spring, by using semi-starved plant material.
- The desire of nursery managers to increase multiplication rates by making use of cutting material that is too small to be set in beds.

Detail of a Eucalyptus nitens seedling root plug grown to plantation readiness in a Plantek 63F tray. Note the fibrous, natural root form obtained by effective lateral air root-pruning.

The side-slot method of achieving lateral root-pruning is a major innovation from Lannen.

- The fact that certain species are better grown in containers when they are destined for particular end uses.

Many countries have not been as fortunate

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in their species choice and climatic conditions to be able to use the bare-root method. For them, container methods have been a necessity, not a choice. New Zealand and Australian foresters are in the fortunate position of being able to tap into the wealth of information available regarding the principles of containerised propagation, without making the expensive mistakes attributed to earlier container designs.

The major factor to consider in any forestry transplant has to be the state of the roots. A natural root form is the desired result. This can be achieved in containers, as with the bare-root method, only by repeated, controlled root-pruning. Resultant root systems after a period of field growth are generally indistinguishable from root systems developed from direct sown trees.

Simply relying on bottom air-pruning is not sufficient to produce a natural root form. More recently, root training guides have been introduced to eliminate root spiraling.

A further step has been the application of a copper-based root-pruning coating on containers with an absorbent surface. But for injection-moulded hard plastic containers, only limited, or short term success has been achieved with copper root-pruning coatings.

The "F"-series of Plantek trays from Lannen are the first trays to incorporate side-slots for air-pruning of lateral roots without the need for chemical treatment. This is a major step towards achieving the desired natural root form for growers using injection-moulded plastic containers.

Understanding side slot benefits

Since their introduction, leading forestry interests have been unanimous in their support for the new range of Lannen Plantek F series trays for the raising of seedlings and cuttings. The same biologically superior Plantek "F" range of trays is now available from our stock in Christchurch and Melbourne. The four models suit all current forestry requirements, as well as many other nursery propagation needs, particularly for the propagation of growing on lines (GOLs) and flowering perennials.

Plantek "F" trays incorporate side slots for air pruning of lateral roots to ensure the growth of a natural root form. This results in vigorous plant growth after transplanting, eliminating concern about root spiralling and other possible deformities.

The design of side slots and the adjacent ribs is an important feature to minimise potential root problems. The presence of the vertical slots ensures that any roots likely to circle in the cell only get a chance to grow as far as the first air-pruning slot.

The potential for roots to grow through the air-pruning slots and to tangle with other roots or grow into

the next cell was considered during the design stage. The resulting design of the interior shape of the slots minimises the chances of roots growing straight across the gap into the opposite cell. Many trials, and three years of commercial propagation have shown that the success with side slot trays relies heavily on nursery management practices. Growing conditions that cause poor or inadequate root pruning are likely to increase the chances of between-cell root entanglement. To get optimum biological results, it is very important to ensure adequate air movement beneath the trays. This will also assist in drying the foliage to prevent disease occurrence by allowing air movement through the vents built between the cells.

The degree of taper in the design of the cells allows for easy extraction of seedlings without damage. The cube-shaped root plug is designed to minimise the risk of transplanter-induced root deformities.

Users can be assured that the range of Plantek trays has been proven in commercial nursery practice in many countries.

Plantek F side slot tray specifications

	63F	64F	81F	121F
External dimensions, mm	397x294x90	384x384x73	384x384x73	384x384x73
Cell volume, cm³	90	115	85	50
Cells per m²	539	434	549	820
Cells per tray	63	64	81	121

Versatile Ecopots

The Ecopot system for containerised plant propagation from Lannen Plant Systems is highly versatile. A major use is for propagating larger seedlings for farm forestry and native species. The option of lateral root control optimises the root growth potential after transplanting.

Different sizes available in the Ecopot range, coupled with the construction method that allows seedlings to be transplanted with no root ball covering, makes the Ecopot system highly effective for other seedlings as well. Asparagus, melon and capsicum seedlings are being grown in the smaller sizes of Ecopot for field transplanting.

Ecopots may be confused with the similar Paperpot system. The primary difference between the two systems is that Paperpots are constructed as a set of paper tubes glued together. For both systems, the sets are stored in a folded position and expanded to give a honeycomb of cells, which, as one unit, is fitted into a growing tray. After a period in the nursery, and when the seedlings are ready for transplanting, it is possible to remove the individual seedlings. For Paperpots, the paper tube protects the seedling during the handling and transplanting stages, while Ecopots give a bare root plug without the effect of the paper wrap.

Rehabilitation of degraded land is an important application where Ecopots are used highly successfully. A range of species, such as grasses, flowering annuals, and perennials can be sown at the same time into the same tray. Mixing of species to achieve a natural combination is not left to the judgment of the transplanting contractor. Small cells, such as the PS410, can generally be used for this purpose, to good effect.

Forestry Transplants

A variation on the bare-root method of forestry transplant propagation is to use a container for the initial establishment phase. These small containerised seedlings or cuttings are lined-out into the normal nursery bed. This method is variously known as plug one in the USA, half/half in Tasmania, or the accelerated transplant method in Finland.

Tasmania Forestry has commenced its second season with the Lannen Plantek "F" trays incorporating lateral air pruning for their half-and-half transplant propagation. Their system uses the Plantek 121F tray.

The main advantage of the accelerated method is that cuttings and seedlings can be started while the nursery beds are still occupied with the previous crop. This gives

Understanding Ecopot and Paperpot terms

PS - standard Ecopot

PSc - Ecopot incorporating lateral root-pruning and is particularly recommended for use with tree species

BS - for 3-6 weeks propagation

VS - Paperpot for 6-9 weeks propagation

FS - Paperpot for 3-12 months propagation

The first digit indicates the cell diameter (some sizes are rounded up or down to a whole centimetre). The second two digits indicate the depth of the cells. For example, PS610 is an Ecopot set with six centimetre diameter and 10 cm depth cells.

Ecopots - showing the construction of the containers and the root ball exposed ready for transplanting.

the chance to produce larger transplants than would normally be the case, and also allows for more efficient land use.

Radiata pine cuttings are generally available for setting before the previous crop has been lifted. Further (and smaller) cuttings may be taken later in the season when environmental conditions are frequently not suitable for setting directly into the nursery beds.

For seedlings, the small plugs can be sown from early July. These will be ready for lining-out in November, ready to take advantage of optimal growing conditions in the nursery beds. This results in seedlings close to a two-year seedling in size, without occupying the nursery beds for this time.

Vegetable and forestry seedlings are easily transplanted with the Pottiputki Planting Tube.

Pottiputki for vegetables

The Lannen Transplanting Tube (Pottiputki) works well for transplanting melons, courgettes, capsicums and tomatoes. Smaller areas of the more intensively grown crops, or even fairly large areas of melons, are quickly and easily transplanted with a minimum of fuss using a Pottiputki.

Most growers would find the No 6 size, internal diameter 61mm, perfect for these seedlings. The upright posture when using the Planting Tubes means no more back pain from having to stoop to transplant seedlings.

The easily adjustable depth limiter allows the Pottiputki to be used for a range of different sized plants. The smooth and natural action results in fast transplanting.

For your own copy of *Growth Points*, or further information on any products or services, please post or fax this coupon to:

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RT-2 Transplanters

The highly popular RT-2 semiautomatic transplanter has proven its worth on many farms, in both New Zealand and Australia. A disturbing practice that appears to be increasing is to allow operators to remain on the machine during moving and repositioning for the next row. This has always been recognised as an unsafe practice and is to be discouraged.

Sitting on the transplanters during repositioning is an unsafe practice.

A dual toolbar is now frequently specified for both new and older RT-2 units. Changes for different row spacings according to the requirements of different crops are made easy where a second toolbar is fitted. All the tractor connections are on the primary toolbar. The secondary toolbar has only the plant rack support arms fitted, leaving the length of the toolbar without obstructions for easy movement of the RT-2 units. Use the coupon if you need more information.

Different soil conditions mean different ploughshares might be needed. The standard short ploughshare supplied with the units has proven to be the most effective for most conditions. A longer ploughshare has been tested under sandy and drier stony conditions to good effect. The longer ploughshare may be the answer if you are having difficulty with too much soil entering the furrow before the seedling is firmed by the press wheels.

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